

A New Adenine Derivative from *Artemisia annua*

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Recently we have reported¹ a new growth inhibitor, cytokinins and lipid constituents from *Artemisia annua* L. (Asteraceae). Now we report the isolation of a novel cytokinin, 6-(3'-methylbutylamino)-2-hydroxy-7,8-dihydropurine (1) from this plant.

Results and Discussion

The methanolic extract of the aerial part of *A. annua* furnished crude cytokinin which was subjected to tlc fractionation. Fraction-1, R_f 0.70, displayed cytokinin activity (103 ng benzylaminopurine equivalent from soyabean callus bioassay). Further purification of this fraction by prep-tlc afforded a homogeneous mass which showed ir bands corresponding to phenolic OH, NH, aromatic and isopropyl functions. The uv spectrum showed maxima (see Experimental). Its mass spectrum had an M^+ ion at m/z 223 ($C_{10}H_{17}N_5O$). The presence of 2-hydroxy-7,8-dihydroadenine moiety was shown by the appearance of the ions at m/z 152 [$C_5H_6N_5O$]⁺ and 153 [$C_5H_7N_5O$]⁺ whereas the ion at m/z 71 indicated a saturated C_5 side-chain. The ter-

minal isopropyl group of the side-chain was evident by the ion at m/z 43 together with the ir bands. The successive loss of the side-chain was indicated by the ions at m/z 43, 57 arising from m/z 71. The isopropyl group resonated at δ 0.85 in the ¹H nmr spectrum and its methine proton was seen at δ 1.65. C-2' methylene protons appeared at δ 1.25 while C-1' methylene appeared at δ 3.35(t). The signal corresponding to hydrogen at C-2 was absent as this position was occupied by an OH group². The NH protons of positions 7 and 9 appeared at δ 8.15 whereas that of position 10 at δ 8.25. The C-8 methylene group flanked by two NH groups was seen at δ 4.35. On biogenetic grounds, the isopentyl chain was linked to N-10 as is the case with other cytokinins. The uv maxima of 2-hydroxyzeatin³ and 2-hydroxy-1'-methylzeatin² appear around 284 nm. In 1 it considerably shifted to lower wavelength due to loss of conjugation showing absence of double bond at C-7.

All these data suggest the structure of 1 as 6-(3'-methylbutylamino)-2-hydroxy-7,8-dihydropurine.

Experimental

Ir spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 FTIR spectrophotometer, uv spectrum on a Pyc-Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer, nmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian FT-80 instrument with TMS as internal standard and mass spectrum on a Finnigan MAT 1020 B spectrometer. Tlc and prep-tlc were performed on silica gel HF 254 (Loba) and the spots visualised by I_2 vapour and uv-light.

The aerial parts (180 g) of *A. annua* (collected from the experimental farm of the authors' Institute) were extracted with methanol (2×800 ml). The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The aqueous phase was extracted with petroleum-ether, b.p. 60–80° (2×100 ml) and the petroleum ether-insoluble material was passed through Dowex 50 WX4 ion-exchange resin H⁺-form (90 g). The column was eluted successively with ethanol (70%; 3 dm³), water (3 dm³) and 3 N NH_4OH (3 dm³). The ammonia eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure to afford cytokinins, purified by repeated prep-tlc in n-BuOH-ammonia-water (6 : 1 : 2, upper phase). Fractions 1, 2 and 3 with different R_f values were obtained. Fractions 2 and 3 were identified earlier¹ as zeatin and dihydrozeatin riboside.

6-(3'-Methylbutylamino)-2-hydroxy-7,8-dihydropurine (1): Fraction 1, viscous mass; ν_{max} ($CHCl_3$) 3300, 3200, 1559, 1542, 1522, 1508, 1380, 1360, 1140, 1060, 733 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 222, 268 (pH 1), 224, 262 (pH 7), 266 nm (pH 12); ¹H nmr δ 0.85 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 1.65 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.25 (2H, m, H_2-2'), 3.35 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, H_2-1'), 8.15 (2H, br s, H-7, H-9), 8.25 (1H, br s, H-10), 4.35 (2H, br s, H-8); m/z (%) 223 [M]⁺ ($C_{10}H_{17}N_5O$, 42), 208 (1), 180 (2), 166 (2), 153 (4), 152 (28), 137 (8), 121 (20), 108 (100), 93 (30), 86 (3), 71 (72), 57 (8), 43 (96).

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